

NUMERICAL EVALUATION OF RESIDUAL MANUFACTURING DEFORMATIONS IN COMPLEX PULTRUDED COMPOSITE PROFILES

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to develop a methodology for numeric evaluation of residual deformations in complex pultruded profiles of composite materials with thermoset resin. With this object in mind, a mathematical model of material behavior is implemented within the ABAQUS environment, accounting for the dependence of matrix thermomechanical characteristics (elastic modulus, coefficient of thermal expansion, heat capacity, thermal conductivity) on the temperature and the degree of polymerization. The rate of chemical reaction of thermoset matrix polymerization is calculated based on a kinetic model. Micromechanical models are used to estimate effective characteristics of a fiber- or fabric reinforced composite within the frames of an anisotropic medium model. Modeling methods developed describe a temperature field distribution, a degree of curing and a stress-strain state in a component during pultrusion process. The method accounts for the contact non-linearity resulting from a possible separation between manufactured component and surfaces of a forming die during polymerization and shrinkage of material.

To illustrate the applicability of the evaluation methods developed an example prediction of warping in a glass fiber reinforced C-shaped profile (400 x 120 x 18 mm) during pultrusion process is presented. Profile reinforcement is built up of fiberglass rovings oriented in a longitudinal direction with the outer layer of fiberglass fabric. Comparison of experimental and calculated data demonstrated a good convergence.

1 INTRODUCTION

Today, structural glass-fiber reinforced plastic (GFRP) components of complex shapes are widely used in aerospace, construction and other industries. Examples of such components include structural elements of composite bridge structures (beams, bridge decking, girders) [1], elements of power line supporting structures of GFRP, elements of aircraft structures, etc. Being rather expensive compared to structures made of traditional structural materials such as wood, concrete and metals, polymer composite structures can nevertheless successfully compete with their traditional counterparts in many applications, especially where the weight or corrosion resistance of a structure is a decisive factor. However they also have to remain cost effective. One way of achieving this goal is the use of large integral structures with low production costs. This approach is feasible and is utilized in various industries, however it requires a good control of process-induced deformations as they may result in deviations of finished item dimensions exceeding specified limits, and, consequently, in problems with fitting of components of complex structures during assembly [2]. The task of producing items with specified shape is usually solved experimentally (by trial-and-error method) through variation of process parameters. Such iterative procedure can be quite expensive, labor-intensive, and ineffective, especially

in case of large components fabrication, thus making the task of developing mathematical models to predict process-induced residual stresses and deformations in composite structures an urgent problem.

2 PULTRUSION

One of the most efficient methods to produce structural profiles of polymer composite materials is a pultrusion process [3]. Pultrusion in principle is a process where a continuous reinforcement (glass fiber roving and tapes) is pulled through an impregnation bath containing thermoset resin and then fed into a heated forming die determining the geometry of pultruded profile cross section, where resin cure takes place (see Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Pultrusion process. Following designations are used: 1 – creels with reinforcement, 2 – impregnation bath, 3 – folding unit, 4 – forming die, 5 – control panel, 6 – pulling unit, 7 – cut-off unit.

Several studies on the application of numerical and experimental methods for thermochemical analysis of pultrusion process have been made earlier [4–17], investigating the distribution of temperatures and curing degree profiles within the heated forming die. The attempts to investigate the thermo-mechanical aspects of pultrusion process such as changes in mechanical properties, stresses, and deformations arising during profile manufacture has been made by Baran et al. [18, 19].

The approaches applied in this study were adopted from the works investigating thermo-mechanical aspects of non-pultrusion processes of composite structures fabrication (autoclave curing, vacuum infusion, and closed die injection), featuring common mechanisms of residual stresses / deformations evolution, similar to that of pultrusion process [20-22].

3 OUTLINE OF PROCESS SIMULATION

To adequately describe changes occurring during manufacturing process in a preform passing through the heated die following phenomena should be taken into account: the transfer of heat into a composite material; chemical reaction of cure; internal release of energy during chemical reaction; temperature and chemical deformations within a preform; thermal and mechanical contact with die surfaces; changes of thermal and mechanical properties of composite material, resulting from phase transformations in a resin. A distinctive feature of simulating the behaviour of composite material with thermoset resin is a necessity to determine the phase state changes in resin over time. To characterize phase state changes in resin a degree of cure, α , (changing in the range from 0 to 1) is used. The cure degree rate of change depends on temperature and on attained degree of cure, and can be expressed by the following kinetic equation:

$$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} = K_0(1 - \alpha)^n \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right), \quad (1)$$

where K_0 – material constant; E – activation energy; n – order of reaction; R – universal gas constant; T – temperature.

Distribution of temperatures within the volume of a preform is determined based on the solution of heat transfer equations:

$$\rho \frac{\partial(c_p T)}{\partial t} = - \sum_i \frac{\partial Q_i}{\partial x_i} + q, \quad (2)$$

where ρ – density; c_p – specific heat capacity of a material; T – temperature; Q_i – heat flux; q – rate of internal heat release (the energy released during cure of thermoset material), i takes values of x, y, z . Constitutive thermal equations (Fourier's law) can be expressed as follows:

$$Q_i = - \sum_j k_{ij} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_j}, \quad (3)$$

where k_{ij} – thermal conductivity tensor of a material, j takes values of x, y, z .

At the same time thermal characteristics (specific heat capacity and thermal conductivity coefficients) depend on temperature and on the attained degree of cure.

The rate of internal heat release is proportional to the rate of reaction of cure and can be expressed as:

$$q = \rho_m H_{tot} \frac{d\alpha}{dt} (1 - V_f), \quad (4)$$

where ρ_m – density of thermoset resin; H_{tot} – specific heat (per unit mass) released at complete cure; $\frac{d\alpha}{dt}$ – rate of reaction of cure; V_f – volume fraction of reinforcement in a composite material.

Mechanical properties of a resin change during solidification. For the purpose of the present work the Poisson's ratio of a resin is assumed to remain constant (as in [19]), while Young modulus E_m is calculated as follows:

$$E_m(T^*) = \begin{cases} E_m^0, & T^* < T_{C1} \\ E_m^0 + \frac{T^* - T_{C1}}{T_{C2} - T_{C1}} (E_m^\infty - E_m^0), & T_{C1} \leq T^* \leq T_{C2}, \\ E_m^\infty, & T^* > T_{C2} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where $T^* = T_g - T$, T_g – glass transition temperature depending on degree of cure and determined from the equation [19]:

$$T_g(\alpha) = T_{g0} + (T_{g\infty} - T_{g0}) \frac{\lambda \alpha}{1 - (1 - \lambda)\alpha} \quad (6)$$

where $T_{g0}, T_{g\infty}, \lambda, T_{C1}, T_{C2}, E_m^0, E_m^\infty$ – material constants determined experimentally.

It is assumed that a coefficient of thermal expansion, β , of an rubbery resin (at $T > T_g$) is 2.5 times higher than CTE of a glassy state. In addition to thermal deformations the so-called chemical deformation (shrinkage) of a composite resulting from rubbery – glassy phase transition of a resin is also considered in calculations [21].

Chemical shrinkage of resin is determined as follows:

$$\Delta \varepsilon_m^{ch} = \sqrt[3]{1 + \Delta V^{ch}} - 1 \quad (7)$$

where $\Delta V^{ch} = \Delta V_{tot}^{ch} \cdot \Delta \alpha$ – resin volume contraction corresponding to the increase in cure degree by $\Delta \alpha$, ΔV_{tot}^{ch} – relative change in a volume of resin at complete cure. Effective chemical shrinkage of a composite is calculated based on analytical models [23].

For stress determination a model of transversely isotropic material is used, where stiffness tensor depends on a phase state of resin (elastic, solid) and changes during cure process. Stiffness tensor at each instant of time is determined as follows: first, the Young modulus of resin is calculated using the equation (3); and then effective characteristics of composite material are calculated based on the

micromechanical model [23]. Mechanical and thermal properties of reinforcing fibers are assumed to remain constant over time.

The model described above is implemented within ABAQUS environment by means of the user subroutine mechanism [24, 25]. As cure processes in thermoset composite materials take place over a long period of time their simulation is carried out using the ABAQUS Standard implicit solver. Thermal conductivity equations are solved using standard ABAQUS tools. The implicit two-step Euler – Cauchy method is used to integrate cure kinetics equation (1).

4 CALCULATION OF STRESS-STRAIN STATE IN A PULTRUDED C-SECTION PROFILE OF BRIDGE STRUCTURES

In this paper the simulation of C-section profile 400x120x18 mm pultrusion process is studied. Profile reinforcement is built up of fiberglass rovings oriented in a longitudinal direction with the outer layer of fiberglass fabric (Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Left: half-section of C-beam with characteristic dimensions. Right: material directions in fabric and roving.

Parameters and constants used in calculations to describe behaviour of composite material constituents (including those in equations (1)–(7)) are taken from [15] and [18], and listed in Tables 1–3.

Following parameters were used in equation (6) for glass transition temperature [18]: $\lambda = 0.4$, $T_{g0} = 0$ °C, $T_{g\infty} = 195$ °C. Distribution of temperatures over the length of forming die is given by experimental data [15] (Fig. 3).

Figure 3: Distribution of temperatures over the length of die.

Parameters		Value
Density of composite	[kg/m ³]	2080
Die length	[m]	1
Pulling speed	[mm/min]	50
Material temperature at the die entrance	[°C]	50
Ambient temperature	[°C]	25
Thermal conductivity coefficients of UD composite material (reinforcement direction 3)	[W/(m·°C)]	$k_3 = 0.9053, k_1 = k_2 = 0.5592$
Thermal conductivity coefficients of in-plane reinforced material (normal to fabric base 2)	[W/(m·°C)]	$k_2 = 0.5592, k_1 = k_3 = 0.73225$
Total thermal effect of reaction of resin cure	[J/m ³]	1.57·10 ⁸
Heat capacity	[J/(kg·°C)]	$976 + 1.68 \cdot T - 178 \cdot \alpha + 0.769 \cdot \alpha \cdot T$
Overall order of reaction by reactants		$n = 1.80$
K_0		4.33·10 ¹³
Activation energy	[kJ/mole]	127.2
Heat transfer coefficient (GFRP / environment; after the die exit)	[W/(°C·m ²)]	14
Volume fraction	[%]	65

Table 1: Parameters used in simulation [4]

Mechanical properties of resin and reinforcement fibers are listed in Tables 2 and 3.

ν_m	T_{C1}, K	T_{C2}, K	E_m^0, MPa	E_m^∞, MPa	$\beta_m^0, 1/K$	$\beta_m^\infty, 1/K$	$\Delta V_{tot}^{ch}, \%$
0.35	-45.7	-12	3.447	$3.447 \cdot 10^3$	$2,5 \cdot \beta_m^\infty$	$5.76 \cdot 10^{-5}$	6

Table 2: Mechanical properties of resin (see equations (5)–(7))

E_f, MPa	V_f	G_f, MPa	$\beta_f, 1/K$
73080	0.22	29920	$5.04 \cdot 10^{-6}$

Table 3: Mechanical properties of reinforcement fiber

Figure 4 shows the degree of cure (left vertical axis) and temperature (right vertical axis) as functions of time (in fabric (solid line) and roving (hashed line)). Vertical line marks the moment the section exits the die. One can see that the resin is fully polymerized at the die exit.

Figure 4: Temperature and degree of cure in fabric and roving as functions of time.

Fig. 5 shows temperature fields (°C) and cure degree fields in a profile cross section at different moments in time. As the section geometry and external influences are symmetric about vertical axis only a half of profile section is shown.

Figure 5: Temperature fields (left) and cure degree fields (right) in a cross section of profile at different moments in time.

One can see that pultruded profile starts to heat up at the die – part interface (contact with the die). At a certain moment in time the maximum temperature zone is shifted toward the inner parts of profile section due to a chemical reaction of cure and corresponding release of heat. This, in turn, affects the distribution of solidification degree fields in resin within the volume of pultruded profile.

Fig. 6 shows deformation of points located in fabric and roving as a function of time. Chemical deformation (shrinkage) is shown in dashed lines and thermal deformation is shown in solid lines. Figure (a) shows deformations in material direction 1, and figure (b) shows deformations in material direction 2 (Fig. 2 left).

Figure 6: Deformation in different locations of profile.

It can be seen that a level of chemical deformations is comparable to that of temperature deformations. The deformations in a direction of reinforcement are twice as smaller compared to those in perpendicular direction. Due to changes in a coefficient of thermal expansion during phase transitions of a resin the temperature deformation does not disappear completely after material is cooled down.

Fig. 7 shows full displacement fields for cross section points after cooling (on mm scale). Maximum displacement comprised 1.35 mm which corresponds to a 0.6° decrease in the angle formed by profile web and leg. Fig. 7 shows the shape of profile after cooling down. Actual displacements are shown at 20x magnification.

Figure 7: Warping of profile after fabrication

Fig. 8 shows predicted stress fields (normal 11 and 22, and shear 12) in a profile section at a finite moment in time (after the profile is cooled down).

Figure 8: Residual stresses fields.

Compressive stresses can be clearly seen in the fig. 8. Tension stresses within roving at the interface with outer fabric layer run as high as 20 MPa (indicating a possibility of cracks formation in roving), while shear stresses at roving – fabric interface run as high as 10 MPa (indicating a possibility of delamination between fabric and roving).

5. EVALUATION OF THE EFFECT OF THE GAP BETWEEN DIE SURFACES AND PROFILE DURING PULTRUSION

As can be seen in Fig. 9, a relatively large air gap is formed between pultruded profile and die surfaces due to temperature deformations and chemical shrinkage.

Figure 9: Gap formation between die surfaces and a profile during heating.

That is why an evaluation of the gap influence on stress–strain state in a pultruded profile requires an additional calculation step accounting for the gap formation. Die – profile heat-transfer coefficient depending on the gap size is calculated as follows:

$$h_c = \frac{k_{air}}{d} \quad (8)$$

where k_{air} – thermal conductivity coefficient of air (0.03 W/(m·K)), d – gap size. The relationship between heat-transfer coefficient and a gap size (in accordance with the model described) is shown in Fig. 10. Maximum heat-transfer coefficient does not exceed 5000 W/(m²·K) which corresponds to the die – profile heat-transfer coefficient in the problem statement described earlier.

Figure 10: Relationship between heat-transfer coefficient and air gap size.

A comparison of time–temperature dependences by thermocouples is shown in Fig. 11.

Figure 11: A comparison of temperatures in points located within angled portion of a profile, both with (dashed line) and without (solid line) regard for air gap influence.

A marked distinction can be seen in the area of internal angle of profile. This distinction is especially noticeable on cure degree plots (Fig. 12).

Figure 12: Degree of cure within angled area of profile calculated with (dashed line) and without (solid line) regard for gap size influence on the die – profile heat transfer.

Thus it may be inferred that taking into account a possibility of gap formation between die and profile caused by temperature and chemical deformations of the last will influence the results of prediction. It should be noted, however, that noticeable distinctions can only be seen in the area adjacent to the internal angle of profile.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In the present work a numerical simulation of the pultrusion process has been studied. A model describing behavior of composite material with thermoset resin has been implemented within ABAQUS environment. A numerical simulation of pultrusion process has been carried out by the example of C-section profile fabrication to evaluate deformations emerging in pultruded part within a forming die and a warpage of finished part. A numerical procedure has been developed to simulate behavior of thermoset composite material under thermal influences. The procedure allows an estimation of products quality at early stages of process design making it possible to introduce necessary corrections to the process.

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